

STRUCTURE, FUNCTIONING AND PROBLEMS OF NICE NATIONAL SPORT MUSEUM OF FRANCE

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Abstract:

Sport is an expression tool of the culture. Historical memory of sport, with its scientific and artistic side, serves as a bridge for societies to reach large masses. In this respect, cultural and sportive movements have led to the establishment of sports museums around the world. Sports museums are a form of expression and a story of a nation. They are the most meaningful bridges between past and future generations. With these aspects, the Nice National Sports Museum of France is one of the representatives in modern countries of sports museology emerged at the end of 19 century. The purpose of the research is to examine the structure, functioning and problems of the Nice National Sports Museum of France, one of the museums in modern countries. In the research, the result has been achieved through the assessment of data, which has been collected by using literature review model and qualitative research techniques within a system. In line with these objectives, the structure of museum, its sections, architecture, comprehensibility, exhibition and richness of cultural and social activities have been presented. The research is important in terms of being as an example of the work to be done on sports museology. As result of the study, Nice National Sports Museum of France has provided different points of view to the sport museology improvement and development, in terms of its structure and functioning, and, with regard to reflecting positive and negative sides of a museum, has become an example for the sport museums to be established with its knowledge, experience and implementations.

Keywords: France, functioning, museum, problem, sport, national

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Introduction and Purpose

These global, cultural and sportive movements, such as painting, music, literature, art and architectural movements, which had emerged with the ancient Olympic Games, have led to the establishment of sports museums. As human activities have got more varied, it has become increasingly important to certify and classify them in the right way. With this understanding, the first sports museums start to emerge at the end of 19th century (Grulich, 2006:81).

Generally, the private collections have constituted the basis of sports museums. Later, this role has been fulfilled by organizations, associations or clubs that created their own archives of particular sports branches. At the same time, the rapid spread of sports and the development of sports equipment encouraged people to collect accurately and systematically all relevant documentation. Despite the need to historical classification of sport, at the beginning the establishment of sports museum has faced great difficulties. Significant challenges have been faced to prove the necessity and benefits of sports museums (Morawinska-Brzezicka, 2012:266).

The background of sports museums are “Cricket Museum” opened at London in 1865 and “Sokol Museum” opened at Prague in 1897. The research, approved by International Olympic Committee (IOC) in 1995, has identified that there were more than 260 sports museums in the world, more than half of which were located at United States of America and Canada. In this context, it came up that there was pretty much interest in sports history in United States of America. Five sports institutions in 1930’s, nine sports institutions in 1940’s, and thirty two sports institutions in 1950’s have been established. In 1960’s, as a huge explosion, the sixty six institutions have been opened. This situation in America has contributed to establishment of new sports museums and of Hall of Honor (Hoffman, 2006:.98).

Halls of Honor have been established at the beginning of twentieth century with the purpose of honor sportive achievements, to exhibit trophies of sportsmen, historical scores, photographs and audio visual documents. The purpose of these museums is to honor figures become legendary in a particular discipline. Also, these museums can be called as modern monuments. Because, by the sport museum visitors they, almost, are regarded as a pilgrimage places. The most important of them are Basketball Hall of Honor, located at Springfield, and Baseball Hall of Honor, located at Cooperstown. Halls of Honors in America have significantly increased since the first opening in Cooperstown New York in 1939 (Ogrozio, 2006:102).

Historically, the oldest sports museum in Europe is Swiss Alps Museum, established in Swiss Bern in 1902. Such factors as geographical location of Swiss, challenges faced by alpinists and their victories have become source of inspiration for

curators of museum. Thus, they reflected the interest to the alpinists and history of Alps on their collections. Especially, the collection of winter sports equipment in Scandinavia countries is not coincidence. Development of skiing as a sport has become real due to these collections. The first skiing museum has been opened in Kristiansand Norway in 1862. Afterwards, the skiing exhibitions, opened in Swiss and Finland, have more encouraged people to go skiing (Morawinska-Brzezicka, 2012: 267).

International Olympic Committee, by making calls for establishing sports museums in Europe in 1922, has provided the necessary steps to establish an Olympic Museum. In this way, Skiing Museum in Norway on 1923, Berlin Sports Museum in Berlin on 1924 and in the same year Physical Education and Sports Museum in the Czech Republic have been opened. In 1927, Horse Museum in Germany and, later, in 1929, Bull Fighting Museum in Spain have been established. In 1950's sports' museums and sport ideas in museums have fully been adopted. This idea has been proved by the sports museums opened one after another (Renson, 2006:89).

The Nice National Sports Museum of France is one of the representatives in contemporary countries of sports museology emerged at the end of 19 century. This museum during 1979-1997 years had been providing service at exhibition gallery in Parc des Princes (Park of Prince), belonging to Paris Municipality, later exhibition area has been closed temporarily until when it take place in 13th arrondissement of Paris with "National Sports Museum" name and in June, 2007 was opened for visitors. However, since the museum was unable to provide enough public services due to its location, the museum on June 27, 2014 has been moved to its new building in Nice.

History and General Information of Nice National Sports Museum of France

The first steps of the National Sports Museum, founded by the secretary of Ministry of Youth and Sport, Maurice Herzog, have been taken in 1963. At those times, Sports Museum had attempted to take place on pages of sports history, without giving much detailed information about its foundation. Maurice Herzog was going to meet the director of the National Museum of Art and former cyclist, Jean Durry, to lay the foundations of future sports museum. Their first activity was to fund the museum and to determine the administrative personnel (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 4).

In fact, eventually, they have managed to collect many collections from different disciplines and to find important documents for National Sports Museum. After the period of preparatory work and collection, collecting of documents, lasted until 1988, the National Sports Museum, during twenty five years, from time to time at special area has presented these objects to people. The various collections of Paris Saint-Germain Football Club and of Rugby teams has been exhibited from 1979 to 1997 at small

exhibition gallery in Parc des Princes (Park of Prince) belonging to Paris Municipality. However, exhibition area was closed temporarily as result of works related to 1998 FIFA World Cup organization. However the fact that it had taken its place in building near the Ministry of Sports in 13th arrondissement of Paris with the name of “National Sports Museum” in 2004, only in June, 2007 it has been opened for visitors (Livre d’introduction, 2016: 4).

The farness of the National Sports Museum building form center of Paris and touristic areas has resulted in lack of visitors dynamic and inability to respond to necessary needs. Because of the farness of National Sports Museum from center of Paris, even Parisians didn’t know about its existence. The museums payment of sum of 3.800 Euros per square meter caused to make exhibition in 700 m² exhibition area and at the same time to limit the institution’s goals in order to welcome visitors. Only 350 of collections from museum’s storage room have been showcased. Therefore, the article of protection of artifacts, which was the main duty of museum, has not been fully provided. The location of the National Sports Museum in 13th arrondissement of Paris and the lack of enough show cases prevented it for having visitors for almost 10 years (Livre d’introduction, 2016: 5).

According to report about museum, between June, 2008 and September, 2009 only 11.173 people have visited the National Sports Museum. During this period, the income from tickets amounted 23.000. The biggest factor that caused this income is the multiple categories applied to visitors and free tickets for children under 18. This situation has caused the National Sports Museum of France to be a complete disappointment in the eyes of other museums which had millions of visitors. Despite the fact that later some progress was record, it didn’t change the fact that the museum couldn’t show performance during the “Paris” period (Livre d’introduction, 2016: 6).

Shortly, the National Sports Museum during half of century period, when it was open, partly has been as a virtual museum. After all these challenges, the state, giving the second chance for sports museum, considered it appropriate to move the museum to new building, located at Nice Football Stadium. So, the National Sports Museum closed its doors on December 29, 2012 to offer to people the best of all in Nice city, the South of France in June 27, 2014. Other cities also have wanted the National Sports Museum to be in their city, but Nice has showed its enthusiasm by reporting that it had all the features required. In 2010, some protocols between Nice Municipality and the National Sports Museum were signed. According to this agreement, Nice Municipality shall undertake construction costs related to museum and intercity transfer of collections and documents (Livre d’introduction, 2016: 6).

Nice city located in southern France, on the Mediterranean coast, between Marseilles and Geneva and is one of the most important touristic centers of France with

population of 374.100. The fact that Nice is a tourist and coastal city had an important role in the movement of the National Sports Museum of France to this region. Transportation to the National Sports Museum of France is provided by bus, railway and taxies. The museum gives service to its visitors from 11.00a.m and 5.00p.m between October and April. The museum is closed on Mondays and during setting and removing period of temporary exhibition gallery. The Nice National Sports Museum is free on the first Sunday of every month from October to April (Museedusport, 2017).

Entrances to the Nice National Sports Museum are provided by passing turnstile. Passing through is possible with the using of small jetton. This jetton remain in jetton boxes, at the end of the day these boxes are emptied, and jetton are counted. In this way, as a method, reflected to statistics, the comparing of ticket numbers sold from ticket offices and jetton reveals the net figure of visitors for every day.

The full cost of museum entrance is 5 Euro for one exhibition and 7 Euro for two exhibitions. Reduced tariff is 2.50 Euro for one exhibition and 3.50 Euro for two exhibitions. The museum is free for children under 18, for people with disabilities, members of Ministry of Culture and Sports and those who work on behalf of Olympic Committee. The reduced tariff is applied for 18-25 years old visitor. Besides, the groups of 10 people can benefit from reduced tariff. But there is one important detail, which is that visitors coming in groups must inform museum about their visiting days at least three weeks before visiting. Thus, the museum with this method, chosen by the museum creates ideal conditions to provide the better and quality service. As a result, based on such parameters group age and institution, the museum provide a working plan.

Nice National Sports Museum can provide guidance service to those who desire. The guidance services are the best chance for visitors to reach to more detailed information related to museum. So, due to guidance service, visitors are able to see every stage of permanent collections and themed temporary exhibitions. The visitors who want to benefit from guidance service for full cost must pay extra 5 Euro for French language and 10 Euro for English, for reduced tariff, they must pay extra 3.50 Euro for French and 8 Euro for English. Similarly, the groups of at least 10 people can benefit from reduced tariff (Museedusport, 2017).

Organization and Administration Structure of the Nice National Sports Museum

The Nice National Sports Museum consist of five departments, such as administration department, human resources department, department of collection, department of research, publications and scientific activity and communication and activity planning department.

Administration department: The Nice National Sports Museum's board of directors, which consists 10 people, is formed as following:

1. Three government representatives: Director of sports or its representative, the representative of minister of sports and representative of minister of culture.
2. District, department and municipality representative: These representatives are selected by the minister of sports from communities which are in cooperation with the National Sports Museum.
3. Two ex-officio members: President of France National Olympic and Sports Committee and president of committee of the Institution.
4. Four authorities appointed by Minister of Sports,
5. One person selected according to rules stated in order of Minister of Sports.

The board members in question can be appointed for renewable period of three years. The representatives of local administrations have a chance to be elected for as long as their term of office. A new member is appointed under the same conditions in more than three month administration gap or in gap formed before the end of term of office. Board of directors is fixed under the instruction of minister of sports. Besides, administrator position is unpaid. Only travel and working expenses are covered by government (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 8).

Human Resources Department: Responsible for providing information about museum to visitors of the museum. At the same time, it has a duty to make various organizations in the framework of pedagogical training workshops, birthday celebrations and cultural activities for children or adult groups.

Department of Collection: This department is responsible for computerizing available or newly acquired documents, recording publications and objects in digital environment to provide update access to database, follow up the date of objects to be displaced within the museum and objects lend to museum and the most important it is responsible for providing thermo-hygrometric standards by creating preventing conditions for objects exhibited or stored in storage rooms.

Department of Research, Publications and Scientific Activity: The most important responsibilities of this department are to make scientific researches necessary for museum (expertise, thematic studies etc.), to design exhibition for museum in cooperation with other institutions, to follow up publications, journals, books, exhibition catalogs, to design traveling exhibitions, to provide information services together with libraries, documentation and archive centers.

Communication and Activity Planning Department: It has such responsibilities as providing corporate and up-to-date communication, making necessary research related to sponsorship and organization of activities to be taken place in the museum.

Nice National Sports Museum has 22 personnel, such as general director of museum, general secretary, 17 officers working at human resources, research, publications and scientific activity and communication and activity planning departments and 3 curators (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 9).

Collection Structure and Exhibition Technique of the Nice National Sports Museum

Since 1963, the Nice National Sports Museum has been realizing its mission of collecting of objects and documents. The big part of collection consist of objects donated by sportsmen, private collections of individuals, books donated by institutions of sports, periodicals, films, photographs and archive documents.

The Nice National Sports Museum has been trying to bring together anthropological, historical and sociological collections for fifty years to get across the sport phenomenon. The oldest materials and documents from these collections with their sizes and diversities date to 16th century. But the most of them dates to 19th and 20th centuries. The sports museum, awarded to Nice city, is accepted as a representative of national heritage of sports. The museum, as a learning domain for history of sports, scientific researches and memory center, tries to satisfy these needs of visitors (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 10).

There are 43.000 objects in the Nice National Sports Museum. About 20.000 poster collection constitutes a significant part of the museum. The important factor in achieving this number is the fact that the first director of museum Jean Durry started to collect artifacts and documents early. This approach, firstly, have represented to us the historic and artistic aspect of the museum (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 10).

Sports gear and equipment which are objects that were the closest witnesses of bravery of a sportsman and personal items of a sportsman has a significant place in collection of the museum. The objects coming into mind when mentioned the sport in society as well as daily objects witnessed France culture are also exhibited in the National Sports Museum.

If to represent the present collection with numbers; 1500 Periodicals, 250.000 Historical brochures, 20.000 Books (dated to 1945 and to previous years) 150 Private archives, 1800 Programs, 110.000 Photographs, 460 Tickets, 1000 Old films and documentaries have taken their places in the museum. Since its foundation in 1960s, the Nice National Sports museum has collected the most unique collection in the world, regarding the surplus of purchased objects and diversity of collected or donated artifacts, chronologically dating to 16th century (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 11).

In the exhibition approach adopted by the Nice National Sports museum there are sections arranged to make an effect on the feel of visitors as well as there are

sections arranged to teach visitors through entertaining. Show case exhibition, models,....., presentations with slides, which are fixed exhibitions techniques regarding presentation technique, have been used. Such dynamic exhibition techniques as demonstration rooms, touch and interactive systems, human carrier vehicles, simulators and digital presentations have been used effectively in the museum (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 11).

The Nice National Sports Museum has 18.000 brochure collection and the most prestigious sports collection in the world, which contains signatures of the many famous sportsmen. Also, the Nice National Sports Museum has more than 3000 sports themed exclusive signed drawings and water color paints. Initially, the collection consisted of certificates from regional championships, but later on the number of certificates reached 1500 due to donations of World and Olympic champions. There are more than 250 sculptures in the museum, which represent sportive activities and belong to such significant artists as Gustave Dore, Alfred Boucher, Pierre Toulgouat (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 12).

The Nice National Sports Museum has 1600 objects (uniforms, shoes, sports gear, accessories etc.), most of which have signatures, donated by champion sportsmen. There are more than 4000 medals, rosettes, cups and prizes. Besides, Olympic medals, which date to 1900, are among collections of the museum (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 12).

Architectural Structure of the Nice National Sports Museum

The Nice National Sports Museum, including Allianz Riviera Stadium, has a total area of 5.860 square meters. Approximately 2.000 square meters of this area has been given to the museum, offering easy-to-understand exhibition space to visitors (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 14).

The museum has a single story structure and is parallel with stadium. The floor of the museum is used as an exhibition area. This creates an ideal environment to provide sufficient lighting and temperature and thermo-hygrometric standards to the objects presented in the museum. In the museum, the temperature is 18 Celsius degree and the humidity rate is 45-55%. Lighting varies depending on the object exhibited and the sunlight effect present itself only in fourth gallery of the museum.

Sections of the Nice National Sports Museum

The National Sports Museum consists of two temporary exhibition galleries and one big permanent exhibition gallery. The big permanent exhibition gallery is divided into four

separate sections. The museum presents temporary exhibition to the people two or three times in a year. The museum has one 200 square meters auditorium, two activity halls, one recreation hall-café, three training activity halls, one saleroom and one storage room (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 15).

In the first section of the exhibition gallery of the permanent exhibition there are objects related to individual sports disciplines. The name of this section is "Self Challenge" because the physical and moral power make from a person a great sportsman. There are gymnastic suits, gymnastic hoops, clubs, bicycles, skiing equipment, sprinter suits, canoes, golf equipment, shoes, belonging to different sports branches, roller skates, equipment and horseshoes belonging to equestrian sports, and various posters.

The name of the second section of the permanent exhibition gallery is "Challenge of Men, Duel". This section is about fighting sports. It houses items related tennis, boxing, wrestling, martial arts and fencing branches. In this section there are tennis rackets, balls, belonging to the champions, tennis sportswear for men and women, boxing gloves, sculptures, posters, fencing jackets, epees, boxing shorts, golden belts, judo jackets, certificates, cups, medals of World and Olympic championship and shoes.

The name of the third section is "Team Spirit is the Spirit of the Self-Sacrifice". This section of the museum presents to the visitors the emotional aspects of the period when France host World Cup in 1998. This section houses football, basketball, handball, volleyball balls, uniforms, shoes, arms, cups of the champion teams and scarves, hats, whistles and drums used by the fans of these teams.

The fourth section of the permanent exhibition "Challenge beyond the Limits". It means to challenge mountains, seas, deserts and sky, to cross the physical boundaries by using technological equipment and devices. As it is understood from the name, it contains objects belonging to champion extreme sportsmen and sportsmen with disabilities who fight with heroism of their hearts. Also, there are sails, canoes, speedboats, race cars, helmets, shoes, chairs of the disabled sportsmen and equipment of the alpinists.

Besides, with 80 seat capacity and with seatless area for 100 people, auditorium satisfies the need of the visitors to watch film and documentary. Also, it is possible to organize various activities (cocktails, seminars, presentations, meetings etc.) on the 150 square meters foreground of the auditorium. It can even be reserved for large sports organizations. For example, it is possible to watch World Cup, European Cup, Olympic Games or grand finals on the giant screen mounted in the auditorium.

Visitors can buy books describing the life of the great champions, signed legendary uniforms, signed books, toys, paintings and mascots in the 100 square meters sales room of the Nice National Sports Museum.

The Young Eagle café, located next to the permanent exhibition and close to the exit, has a unique concept of the recreation environment. Posters, uniforms, scarves, of the legendary teams, match tickets, games, photographs with the beautiful presentation and music for the last time invite visitors to enjoy the museum. At the same time, the table football game pleasure, tea and coffee pleasure from beverage maker, pleasure of watching interactive screens are another services offered to the visitors.

Educational, Cultural and Social Activities Organized in the Nice National Sports Museum

There are three 100 square meters workshops in the Nice National Sports Museum providing pedagogical education. Up to the present, lots of themes have been handled in these workshops. The 2016 European Football Championship training which has been organized for children is the one of the examples.

Educators have developed various educational tools to describe the championship to the children. They have prepared a 50 paged booklet describing football history, teams and fans. Also, to create sports awareness through teaching, sports bag with balls, whistles, uniforms, cards have been presented to each child. Besides, teaching games organized by the educators, also, have provided an opportunity for children to spend time amusingly and usefully (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 17).

The most not themed, important activity, taught to children in the permanent workshops, was the activity of inventing their own games without looking at present sports games models. For example, how to play on the triangle field? Or, is it possible to play basketball with child scooter? These kinds of activities, which designed to encourage children to be creative and to make them to think about rules of the game, are provided. From the other hand, by performing Olympic ceremony for each child and giving the medal, it becomes possible to be part of the excitement caused by Olympic spirit. In addition to all these educational activities, the Nice National Sports Museum is also host the people in the framework of birthday celebrations.

The Nice National Sports Museum offers a game room for visitors of all ages, as well as the opportunity to benefit from simulated sports branch application. In the game room there is a table football, which is the very famous football game. This game room, located at the end of the third hall and which allow visitors to feel the spirit of the team sports, presents moments of pleasure to the visitors. Simulated fencing sports, located at the end of the first section, in the small hall, have succeeded in making people as almost exited as the fencing sportsmen feel by doing this kind of sport.

The Budget and Visitors Statistics of the Nice National Sports Museum

The museum and Nice Municipality have made an agreement in 2013 to realize the project of movement of the sports museum from 13th arrondissement of Paris to the Nice city. According to this agreement, the Nice Municipality granted 4.500.000 Euro to the sports museum with the condition of controlling the institution's business and repayment within determined period (10 years). Total of the budget received from the government and the budget of the museum is 3.930.000 Euro. With the grant of the Nice Municipality the amount of the budget have reached 8.430.000 Euro. So the museum has come to these days with the budget of 8.430.000 Euro (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 19).

Table 1 & 2: Amount of Money Paid for Nice National Sports Museum

Year	Amount (Euro)	Institutions
2012	143 151	Grant from Sports Activities
2013	1 256 849	Grant from Government
2013	600 000	Net Working Capital Net of the Nice National Sports Museum
2013	1 500 000	Grant from Government
2014	430 000	Net Working Capital Net of the Nice National Sports Museum
Total	8 000 000	

Summary	
Government/Museum	3 930 000 Euro
Nice Municipality	4 500 000 Euro
Total	8 430 000 Euro

Source: Archive of the Nice National Sports Museum (2015)

The income of the Nice National Sports Museum is provided as follows:

The income earned form public institutions, donations of private and legal persons, grants of government, cultural activities organized by institutions, performances and various sportive activities, pedagogical trainings, formations, donations, testaments, wealth fun and visitors is constitutes the account of the museum.

During the 30 months period from the opening date of the Nice National Sports Museum on June 27, 2014 to December 31, 2016 1.130.000 people have visited the museum. The 41% of these visitors were 18-25 age group and 17% under 18 years old. This numbers demonstrate that social, educational and cultural activities of the museum satisfy the needs of the young people. The rest 16 % constitutes 25-35 age group and 26% consist of group over 35 years old people (Livre d'introduction, 2016: 20).

The Problems of the Nice National Sports Museum

The biggest problems of the Nice National Sports Museum are the financial support and budget problems arising from wrong government policy. Accordingly, performance agreement valid until 2010 have caused the museum to provide service in the 13th arrondissement of Paris and prevented it from sufficient development. But the biggest disagreement is that government placed the sports museum on the same position with other museums in France. So it is not fair to expect the same performance from the 700 square meters museum, which is not located in the touristic area and from the Louvre Museum and Orsay Museum, which have millions of visitors in a year. Therefore, according to agreement, the small number of the visitors of the museum, located in Paris, constitutes insufficient financial support from the government.

This situation has allowed minister of state responsible for sports to move the museum. The Nice National Sports Museum has got new structure with the agreement and law amended to remove obstacles of financing problems. After the Nice Municipality granted budget of 4.500.000 Euro the museum has moved to Nice city. Recently, 15 % of this amount has been paid. The government must clarify its fiscal targets so the museum could pay the rest of the debt to the Nice Municipality.

Conclusion

After the examination of the general structure of the Nice National Sports Museum of France it has been identified that the administrative personnel of the museum and organization sections work in cooperation with each other, work distribution function among units is preserved and that the diversity of objects and documents archive of the exhibition approach integrates with audio visual communication technologies. The museum with its architectural structure and sections presents to the visitors an easy-to-understand exhibition area as well as the principle of viewing of all exhibition area by the visitors during their tour has been taken into consideration. Teaching, cultural and social activities made under framework of functioning of the Nice National Sports Museum of France have provided special trainings to the children and young and such activities, where adults can participate, as conferences, cocktails, seminars and meetings. The museum with its structure and functioning has created a new point of view for development of the sports museology. After the examination of the problems of the National Sports Museum, it has been identified that the wrong museum policy affects negatively the budget of museum, and this situation, afterwards, creates some problems in providing sufficient services for visitors. In conclusion, the Nice National Sports Museum of France, in terms of reflecting its positive and negative aspects, with

its knowledge, experience and implementations serves as a model for museums to be established in the future.

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